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Responsible Partner: Anses

Contributing partners: ISS, FLI, INIAV, BIOR, IZSS,
UT, CVRL, UZ, PIWET

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ASSESSMENT OF NEWLY DEVELOPED MOLECULAR METHODS AGAINST THE EXISTING TECHNIQUES

1. Introduction

1.1. Epidemiological context

Since 30 years and the development of the first molecular techniques for the detection of *Echinococcus* DNA, the molecular diagnostic became essential. There are currently a lot of molecular assays to detect DNA of *Echinococcus* species targeting especially *E. multilocularis* (Em) and *E. granulosus sensu lato* (Eg sl) by end-point PCR, PCR RFLP and more recently real-time PCR. Depending the type of assays sequencing can be required or not, it can be methods specific for one species or more by simplex or multiplex approaches. The nature of the matrix classically used is tissue (larval stage or worms) and fecal sample.

There is no currently gold standard or reference methods for molecular diagnostic of *Echinococcus* species DNA, even if a few numbers of methods are more used than the others. In view of the diversity of existing methods and their relevance, as well as the development of new methods within the framework of the EJPOH Meme project, a comparison of these methods could lead to recommendations and a harmonization of molecular diagnostic techniques.

1.2. References

Bowles et al. 1992

Knapp J, Umhang G, Poulle ML, Millon L. Appl Environ Microbiol. 2016. Development of a Real-Time PCR for a Sensitive One-Step Coprodiagnosis Allowing both the Identification of Carnivore Feces and the Detection of *Toxocara spp.* and *Echinococcus multilocularis*. doi: 10.1128/AEM.03467-15.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

One DNA panel from tissue samples and one from fecal samples were realized by the Anses. The DNA extraction were realized using an automated DNA extraction using magnetic beads and dedicated kits for tissue and feces. Tissue samples were obtained from isolated worms from fox or wolf intestine and larval stage from livestock, mice, nutria, macaque and lemur. Fecal samples were obtained from wolf naturally infected by Eg *sensu stricto* (ss), from fox experimentally infected by Em and from naïve fecal samples of fox from the experimental station. For each sample, a control by both Em and Eg sl specific real-time PCR (Knapp et al. 2016, Maksimov et al. 2020) for all *Echinococcus* samples and for short cox1 PCR (Bowles et al. 1992) for others cestode and nematode species. Three DNA extractions for each sample were pooled to obtain the final tube for the panel. The final tissue panel was composed of 54 DNA samples including 4 nematode species, 7 cestode species others than *Echinococcus* in addition to Em, *E. equinus*, *E. ortleppi* and different genotypes of Eg ss (G1, G3), *E. canadensis* (G6, G7, G10).

The copro-DNA panel was composed of 20 samples. In addition, protoscoleces of Em and Eg ss were used to produce each one tube of DNA at 10ng/μl used to evaluate the limit of detection.

Table 1: List of the parasite species and number of samples constituting the tissue and fecal DNA samples panels

Type of matrix	Class of species	Parasite species	Nb of samples
Tissue	Nematode	<i>T. canis</i>	3
		<i>F. hepatica</i>	1
		<i>F. gigantica</i>	1
		<i>T. leonina</i>	5
		<i>A. incisa</i>	3
		<i>M. lineatus</i>	1
		<i>M. litteratus</i>	3
		<i>H. kamyai</i>	3
	Cestode	<i>H. taeniaeformis</i>	3
		<i>T. krabbei</i>	3
		<i>T. hydatigena</i>	4
		<i>Em</i>	7
		<i>Eg ss G1</i>	3
		<i>Eg ss G3</i>	2
		<i>E. equinus</i>	2
		<i>E. ortleppi</i>	3
Feces	Cestode	<i>E. canadensis G6</i>	3
		<i>E. canadensis G7</i>	3
		<i>E. canadensis G10</i>	1
Feces	Cestode	<i>Em</i>	6
		negative	2
		<i>Eg ss (+Taenia sp.)</i>	12

2.2. Methods

The selection of the methods was realized by concertation between Anses, FLI and ISS (Table 2). The aim was to evaluate the specificity, sensitivity. First the methods selected had to be realised at least in two institutes between Anses, FLI and ISS and in a second time partners were invited to contribute for evaluation of any of these selected methods. The only inclusion criteria for invited partners was that the method has to be already performed in routine so it can be considered to be under control. Finally ten participants were concerned. The DNA extraction was not concerned as each lab has received the same panel of DNA to evaluate the techniques. A dedicated sheet was send to each lab in order to explain the aims of the study and described globally the DNA panel.

Table 2: List of the methods selected for the evaluation and laboratory involved.

Type of assay	Name of the test	Reference	Targeted species	Laboratories involved in the evaluation
End point PCR	Multiplex Cest	Trachsel et al. 2007	Em, Eg sl, Taenia spp.	ISS, FLI, ANSES + INSA, BIOR, IZSS, UT, CVRL, UZ, PIWET

Real-time PCR	qPCR-Em	Knapp et al. 2016	Em	ANSES, FLI, PIWET
Real-time PCR	qPCR-Em MGB	Isaksson et al. 2014	Em	ANSES, FLI
Real-time PCR	qPCRs Eg sl	Maksimov et al. 2020 (WP3-T2-ST1)	Eg sl	ANSES, FLI

3. Results

3.1. Cest Multiplex PCR to detect *E. multilocularis* and *E. granulosus sl* from Trachsel et al. 2007

The results are homogeneous between participants and correct for tissue samples excepting some rare errors resulting to high specificity values (Table 3). Regarding the sensitivity, if high values were obtained for tissue samples it is lower for copro-DNA with half of the samples detected for both Em or Eg sl.

Table 3: Specificity (SP) and sensibility (SE) values for Em and Eg sl regarding the tissue and feces DNA panels.

	Lab#1	Lab#2	Lab#3	Lab#4	Lab#5	Lab#6	Lab#7	Lab#8	Lab#9	Lab#10	Average	Average T/F
SP Em tissue (n=47)	96%	100%	100%	98%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	98%	99%	99.3%
SP Em feces (n=14)	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
SP Eg sl tissue (n=37)	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	92%	95%	97%	100%	100%	98%	98.7%
SP Eg sl feces (n=8)	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
SE Em tissue (n=7)	100%	100%	86%	86%	100%	86%	100%	100%	100%	86%	94%	75.4%
SE Em feces (n=6)	100%	67%	67%	17%	33%	33%	0%	67%	67%	83%	53%	
SE Eg sl tissue (n=17)	94%	94%	94%	100%	94%	94%	94%	100%	100%	100%	96%	77.2%
SE Eg sl feces (n=12)	67%	50%	67%	42%	33%	8%	50%	50%	58%	75%	50%	

3.2. Real-time PCR to detect *E. multilocularis* from Isaksson et al. 2014

The global specificity observed is low (76.1%) due to the results obtained by the two participants with tissues samples (45% and 69%) mainly due to cross reactions with Eg sl samples but also some others parasite species. There is a difference of Ct values between nonspecific detections in tissue samples (Ct between 31 and 40) with very high DNA concentrations and the Ct values obtained for copro DNA (Ct between 12 and 36) with low target DNA concentration. The sensitivity is 100% for both types of samples and for the two participants.

Table 4: Specificity (SP) and sensibility (SE) values for Em regarding the tissue and feces DNA panels.

	lab#1		lab#2		Global	Global T/F
	%	Ct values	%	Ct values		
Sp Em tissue (n=47)	45%	31-40	94%	32-37	69%	76,10%
SP Em feces (n=14)	100%	/	100%	/	100%	
SE Em tissue (n=7)	100%	déc-20	100%	14-23	100%	100%
SE Em feces (n=6)	100%	23-34	100%	27-36	100%	

3.3. Real-time PCR to detect *E. multilocularis* from Knapp et al. 2016

3.4. Real-time PCR to detect *E. granulosus* sI from Maksimov et al. 2020

4. Discussion